

Number of cases of COVID-19 in the Philippines

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The Philippines is one of the nations that struggle to contain the spread of Coronavirus Pandemic.

In Southeast Asia, Philippines is second to Indonesia by the most number of confirmed COVID-19 cases as of today 18 April 2020.

Source:

<https://www.npr.org/sections/coronavirus-live-updates/2020/04/17/836783432/indonesia-now-has-the-most-confirmed-covid-19-cases-in-southeast-asia>

As of today, 18 April 2020, the Philippines has recorded 5,878 confirmed cases of covid19. The number of fatalities is 387 and the number of recoveries is 487.

According to the report presented by Philippines department of health to the World Health Organization dated 15 April 2020:

- Out of the total 5,453 confirmed cases reported in the Philippines until today, 55% are male, with the most affected age group 60-69 years (19.7%)
- Out of the 349 confirmed deaths, 69.5% are male, with the most affected age group over 70 years (33.7%)

So what are the Department of health and the allied agencies doing to contain the situation?

1. DOH is closely monitoring individuals who manifested signs of respiratory infection and had a history of travel to China, and is coordinating with WHO and China Center for Disease Control for updates.
2. DOH is also enhancing its coronavirus laboratory testing capacity, hospital preparedness, rapid response, and its risk communication and information dissemination. Personal Protective Equipment are made available at the Bureau of Quarantine, Centers for Health Development, and DOH Hospitals.
3. The Bureau of Quarantine, meanwhile, is working with airlines and airport authorities to strengthen border surveillance, while the Epidemiology Bureau is heightening its community surveillance.

Source: <https://www.doh.gov.ph/2019-nCov/FAQs>

The Department of Health is not alone in the fight of coronavirus.

The Philippines congress enacted the Bayanihan to Heal as One Act through a special session on 23 March 2020. This act authorized the President to exercise powers necessary to carry out urgent measures related to the Covid-19 situation. This law allows the president to "reallocate, realign, and reprogram" a budget of almost ₱275 billion (\$5.37 billion) from the estimated ₱438 billion (\$8.55 billion) national budget approved for 2020.

The Government needs an enormous budget to sustain the growing number of Personal Protective Equipment by the frontliners, the medicines, the health care facilities and

transportation of the frontliners and the affected COVID-19 persons.

Businesses are temporarily closed

Large and small business sectors, public and private companies have been temporarily closed. This includes the public transportations and Establishments. People are ordered to stay at home. All of these are being done to contain the spread of coronavirus and yet the number of affected persons is continuously increasing.

So what is lacking? Why does the number of confirmed covid-19 cases suddenly spike?

Well, in my personal opinion, the reason why the Philippines Covid-18 cases continuously increasing is because of the following:

1. Department of Health (DOH)

Late advice of the Department of Health to place the Philippines especially the capital region into quarantine. Before the coronavirus outbreak, we heard a number of cases reported from our neighboring countries. Some Nations already imposed strict national quarantine yet the Philippines continues to engage its daily activities. No social distancing, no proper plans or actions and most importantly there was no travel ban imposed from entering the country. So the carrier of the virus continues

to roam around the country unknowingly affecting the people around them.

2. People of the Philippines

Some of my fellow countrymen despite the national orders to stay at home during the Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ) continue to go outside. The number of violators during the ECQ exceeds 100,000 - Philippines National Police.

From March 17 to April 10, the total number of violators was recorded at 101,974.

This is broken down to:

Luzon: 60,040

Visayas: 18,514

Mindanao: 23,420

Source:

<https://www.gmanetwork.com/news/news/nation/733559/number-of-violators-during-enhanced-community-quarantine-exceeds-100-000-pnp/story/>

Most of these violators are forced to go outside to find foods for their daily consumption. The poor families are most affected during this crisis. No savings, no livelihood and no foods. Imagine, when you wake up every morning, your first problem is how to feed your family for the whole day.

In the televised public address of President Duterte on late Monday night, 30 March 2020, he said that "We have allotted

₱200 billion for low income households who are badly affected by this crisis. Beneficiary households will receive emergency support for their two months based on the regional minimum wage,”.

The Department of Social Welfare and Development is tasked to implement the 5000-8000pesos social amelioration program to help the Poor communities cope up for their daily living while the state is under the enhanced community quarantine.

But despite the financial assistance, there are still community quarantine violators.

Conclusion

So is it safe to conclude that the continuous increase of confirmed COVID-19 cases is due to poor responses i.e lack of comprehensive plannings and actions or is it because of some uncooperative citizens?

In this time of global pandemic, the best and effective approach to stop COVID-19 from killing many lives is COOPERATION among stakeholders that includes the citizens who the state and the government specially the frontliners are protecting so much even the cost of their lives.